

Creating a collection of albums on the CERN Document Server from digitized historical photos of particle tracks

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

Tens of thousands of images of particles tracks from the 1970s have been digitized in 2024 and stored on the CERN Data Cloud (EOS). They are grouped into folders corresponding to the envelopes in which they were stored and are named with the information printed on the back of each photo. The student will have to analyze the set of images, design a process to create albums and records, and finally implement the programs enabling the upload of all the photos into a public collection of the CERN Document Server. It will therefore give these images a new audience, as they will become available online.

ABSTRACT

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We present the digital integration of the Tracks Images collection, a recently digitized set of photographs documenting CERN's early history through tracks captured in Hydrogen Bubble Chambers, into the CERN Document Server. Our workflow incorporated insights from the collection's analog envelope structure into MARCXML records using the OpenRefine framework. MARCXML records were constructed and enriched with basic metadata fields, while an image similarity algorithm was applied to identify and cluster near-duplicate scans arising from the multiplicity of negatives. The resulting clustered dataset was used to generate representative records for upload. In total, 6365 image records covering 5339 envelopes were published on the CERN Document Server, ensuring their long-term preservation and visibility. This project presents a pipeline for large-scale digitized image collection processing and lays the groundwork for future improvements in similarity benchmarking, keyword-based metadata enrichment, and expert-driven curation.

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(a) The compactus layout of the archives. Photo by the CERN Scientific Information Service [13]

(b) Storage units (cardboard boxes, binders, shelves) in a compactus. Photo by Danaé Broustail.

Figure 1: The CERN archives.

1 Introduction

Images, videos, and audio recordings have been accumulated at CERN since its foundation in 1954. These analog materials were initially stored in cardboard boxes, distributed across various storage rooms at CERN. Over time, they were progressively identified and transferred to compacti in the archives (see Figure 1), where particular care was taken to preserve their physical integrity through the use of non-acidic storage materials and controlled humidity and temperature conditions [13].

Analog materials such as tapes, photo slides, and negatives carry a unique historical value: they document the story of CERN's predecessors, and serve as a testament to the evolution of engineering and physics to fulfill CERN's mission. Since 2016, several preservation phases have been carried out to digitize these collections, with a dual objective: to conserve unique historical data, preventing deterioration and loss of information, and to share CERN's rich history to a wider audience. This work is embedded in the larger-scale Digital Memory project [3], conducted by the Institutional Repositories section in CERN's Information Technology department.

1.1 The particle tracks collection

The particle tracks collection, which is the main focus of this report, is one of the last analog collections to undergo digitization. Its digitization was delayed because the collection lacked detailed captions and a clear historical context. In 2024, the collection was scanned by Scan-Corner India, a company specializing in digitizing analog photo formats. The original photos were stored in labeled envelopes or taped into binders, often with a handwritten date beneath each image (see Figure 3).

The collection contains highly heterogeneous material spanning several decades of CERN history: color and grayscale photographs of personnel, sites, and machines; experimental apparatus diagrams; hand-drawn graphs; handwritten notes; mathematical proofs; and, at its core, the particle tracks themselves (see Figure 2).

The particle tracks were produced by hydrogen bubble chamber experiments [14]. The hy-

Figure 3: Storage structure of the collection. Envelope labels are a combination of numbers and letters. They typically contained multiple negatives of the same image, either in medium format or in film format (26 x 35 mm). Photos were found in binders and their label was a date caption.
Photos by Danaé Broustail.

Figure 4: The CERN Photolab page on CDS.

1.3 Goal and motivation

Our aim is to upload the heterogeneous, metadata-limited particle tracks collection to CDS, both to visually showcase CERN’s heritage and to enrich these digitized images with as much contextual information as possible, transforming them into contextualized digital records.

(a) The folder structure of the digitized collection, showing the digital image contents of envelope 10074. The scans of envelope 10074 are almost identical due to the presence of several negatives within the same envelope.

(b) Negatives (film and medium format) stored in envelope 10074.

Figure 5: Comparing the structure of the analog and digital collections, with envelope 10074. In the digital collection, each negative scan is uniquely identified by its envelope number and its number suffix in the `envelopeNb_tirageNb` format, where `envelopeNb` is the envelope number and `tirageNb` is the print number, also known as the tirage number. A photo of the envelope label is also provided, with a filename format of `envelopeNb_Label`.

Photos by Danaé Broustail.

2 Data exploration

In this section, we will describe the exploratory data analysis of the collection. We first explored the collection's structure and existing metadata. We then investigated correlations between the digitized collection and its analog counterpart stored in the CERN Archives. Finally, we refined the scope of the project following these insights.

2.1 Description of the collection

The photos of the collection were scanned and digitized into TIF images. The TIF format is an image file format known for its ability to store high-quality images, making it a suitable choice for archiving. This choice led to file sizes in the range of 60 MB, making it impossible to download the full dataset locally. We used the Linux Public Login User Service (LXPLUS [10]), a cluster of Linux PCs provided by the CERN IT department, to access the images. We accessed the images remotely by mounting the collection on LXPLUS from its storage directory on EOS (see Code Snippet 1).

```
mkdir PHOTOS
eosxd -ofsname=eosmedia.cern.ch:/eos/media/cds/public/www/digital-memory/media-archive/
↔ image/ScanCorner-mirror/PHOTOS PHOTOS
cd PHOTOS
```

Listing 1: Mount command for the collection dataset. Executed from the command line of my LXPLUS user space.

The digitized collection was uploaded to EOS in nine batches, each named according to "PHOTOS.N" where N was a number ranging from 1 to 9. A PHOTOS batch contained album

(a) Envelope Media Description table (left) loaded in OpenRefine, showing first 8 rows. TIF EOS file path table (right) loaded in OpenRefine, showing first three rows.

(b) OpenRefine dataframe of TIF file paths, augmented with the album folder name "TIF Album ID" and filename "TIF filename". This diagram shows how the album folder name (equivalent to the envelope name) and filename of a TIF image can be extracted from a TIF file path.

Figure 6: OpenRefine Metadata tables.

folders where TIF image scans were stored (see Figure 5a). Each PHOTOS batch contained around 500 to 1000 album folders.

The album folder structure mirrored the envelope structure of the analog collection: the name of each album folder corresponded directly to a physical envelope label in the collection and reflected the contents of that envelope. An album folder contained scans of the negatives stored in the corresponding envelope, along with a photo of the envelope label itself (see Figure 5b). For example, a folder named 10074X contained digitized scans of the negatives originally stored in envelope 10074X in the physical collection (see Figure 5).

This structure preserved valuable information about the storage context of the images, which we considered an important form of metadata. We also observed that the digitization process retained the multiplicity of negative prints, resulting in near-identical image scans (see Figure 5).

2.2 Metadata exploration

2.2.1 Available metadata for envelopes

Scancorner provided envelope-level metadata in Excel sheets for each PHOTOS batch, covering around 5,400 album folders. Each .xlsx file was structured as a dataframe, indexed by the folder name in the Folder Name column, with a Media Description column describing the contents of each envelope (see Figure 6a).

The Media Description column contained comma-separated strings listing up to three medium types and their respective counts per envelope. This dataframe will hereafter be referred to as the Media Description table. The three types of medium were:

- Medium format negatives (approximately 11×13 mm)
- Film negatives (26×35 mm)
- Developed photos

2.2.2 Metadata for images

Although there were no metadata available for the image files other than the envelope ID, the digitized dataset provided a list of TIF file paths in a .txt file (see Figure 6a).

At first glance, this offered no additional metadata in addition to what was already known. However, we observed that file paths presented ground-truth information on the inclusion relationship of files within album folders (see Figure 6b). This was a robust way of determining the true envelope containment relationship in cases where image files were affected by naming errors.

Indeed, upon inspecting the filenames and the value counts of the filename occurrences, we discovered that there were multiple types of file naming anomalies, which fell into the following categories:

Duplicate filenames Filenames that occurred more than twice across the collection.

Duplicate scans Some folders were scanned twice with slight changes in the album folder name, e.g. 1-04-65X and 01-04-65X.

Wrong envelope number in filename The envelope ID of the filename did not match with the album folder name, e.g. a 25631X_005 filename in a folder named 25431X.

Wrong album folder name The name of the album folder does not match with the photo of the real envelope label, e.g. a 25292X envelope name in contrast to a 25929X envelope label photo.

Unstructured filenames Filenames that did not conform to the `envelopeNb_tirageNb`.

Missing print number or envelope name e.g. a file with a single underscore "_".

Minor format errors e.g. 41456X_X001 and "10343X_002 (2)".

File lacking an underscore e.g. 10058X002.

Unmatched envelope ID to Media Description There are no entries in the Media description table that match with the envelope ID extracted from the filename.

Single character or number differences e.g. 1-4-56X instead of 1-5-56X.

Separator differences e.g. 01.3.58X extracted from the filename and 01-3-58X in the Media Description table album folder name.

2.2.3 Metadata insights from the archives

By visiting the archives, we were able to identify patterns in the image metadata through direct inspection of the analog collection. The physical items in the digitized collection were preserved in the archives in their original storage format, either within envelopes or taped to binders.

In the case of binders, we closely inspected the photos and analyzed the handwritten notes explaining the event context (see Figure 7a). By matching the various notes and the image caption beneath the photos, we deduced that the captions could be parsed as dates in the format of "day-month-year".

However, we discovered counterexamples to this format (see Figure 7 for an explanation). The first dash-separated part of the caption could correspond to an image number rather than a specific day of the month. For the images of our collection, this remained an open question (see Section 6).

(a) Binder containing photos. Captions are three dash-separated numbers. Handwritten notes on event context are written in French.

CERN PhotoLab / Personalities and History of CERN CERN-HI-5405001

**First excavation work on Meyrin site
Les premiers coups de pelle !**

Date: 15 May 1954

Geneva was selected as the site for the CERN Laboratory at the third session of the provisional Council in 1952. This selection successfully passed a referendum in the canton of Geneva in June 1953 by 16539 votes to 7332. On 17 May 1954, the first shovel of earth was dug on the Meyrin site under the eyes of Geneva officials and members of CERN staff

Genève fut choisie pour accueillir le site du CERN lors de la troisième session du Conseil provisoire, en 1952. En juin 1953, ce choix fut entériné au terme du référendum organisé dans le canton de Genève et qui donna 16539 voix pour et 7332 voix contre. Le 17 mai 1954, les premiers coups de pelle étaient donnés sur le site de Meyrin en présence de personnalités officielles du Canton de Genève et de membres de personnel du CERN

Keywords: CERN50

Related links:

CERN Courier vol. 44 no 8 : October 2004
Original ref.: 01-5-54

Conditions of Use © 1954-2025 CERN
Accessing copyrighted material

Total images: 1

CERN-HI-5405001-1
Small, Medium, Large, Original

(b) CDS record of the 01-05-54 photo on the top right of 7a. The date of the event is the 15th of May 1954.

Figure 7: Comparison between binder-taped photos and CDS records.

We see a slight contradiction between the 01-05-54 caption on the construction photo on the top right of 7a, which is recorded as 15th May 1954 on CDS in 7b. The photos on the left page of 7a have 54 in the third part of their caption, suggesting a year of 1954. The first part of the caption, ranging from 1 to 3 from top to bottom contrasts with the handwritten note in French that this is the first council meeting in Geneva on the 7th to 8th of October.

Photo of binder by Danaé Broustail. Image record taken from CDS Photos, with a search query on the year 1954.

(a) Listing of figure descriptions. Figure IDs are five-digit labels.

(b) Front page of a scientific report named "CERN-TC-PHYSICS-63-4-collision".

(c) Captioned collision photo, in the "CERN-TC-PHYSICS-63-4-collision" report.

Figure 8: The list document of figure captions and the scientific report referencing images of particle tracks. "CERN-TC-PHYSICS-63-4-collision" is available on CDS [9]. The listing document was provided by Sandrine Reyes (CERN Scientific Information Service) and scanned by Danaé Broustail.

In the case of envelopes, additional insight was provided by the CDS archives "Particle collisions" [11] collection, which holds 120 particle track images with detailed descriptions. By discussing with the team in charge of retrieving and documenting these records, we discovered that the captions were provided through list documents (see 8a), which contained captions for every figure that would be referenced in a report (see 8b and 8c for a report with an embedded figure). Furthermore, the figure IDs used in this document had a five-digit structure similar to that of a subset of our envelope IDs.

From our visit to the archives, we concluded that the caption-lacking collection may consist of unused residual figures, as the envelope names share a similar format with figure reference IDs. In addition, we discovered that a subset of the digitized collection included date-formatted captions, present both in filenames and envelope names, that could be extracted and used as metadata.

2.3 Challenges and decisions

To conclude the data exploration section, we summarize the main challenges identified and the decisions made to address them, which in turn shaped the project's outline.

The first challenge was the lack of captions and detailed historical metadata in the dataset, apart from a small subset of images that included dates.

To address this, we focused on restoring the original storage context metadata, i.e. identifying which images belonged to the same envelope. We chose to construct MARC fields directly from the TIF file paths of the images, using the OpenRefine framework [5] to perform record-wise transformations and string operations. This process generated MARC fields as features within a TIF file path table, which could then be combined into MARC snippets. For MARC fields requiring uniqueness (such as the report number, i.e. the document name) we corrected duplicate and erroneous filenames, while keeping alterations minimal in order to preserve original naming. For MARC fields requiring direct access to image data, we applied external transformations by iterating over the TIF file paths, loading images from the

file system, and extracting additional metadata. We envisioned these transformations producing dataframes that could be imported into OpenRefine and joined to the main TIF file path dataframe containing the MARC fields.

The second challenge concerned the selection of images for upload to CDS, with the aim of maximizing the value and readability of the collection.

Because many negatives had multiple prints, near-duplicate scans risked overloading the CDS display if all images were uploaded. To prevent this, we decided to investigate image similarity across the collection and apply filtering transformations to retain only representative and relevant samples. This led us to focus solely on image records and to discard album records. However, we chose to preserve envelope-level context by including containment relationships in the notes and related references of the image records. We also discarded the `envelopeNb_Label` files, as they did not add significant value to the collection.

In summary, the data exploration stage led us to outline the project as follows: (1) extract MARC fields from TIF file paths, (2) ensure correctness and uniqueness in required fields, and (3) run external scripts over file paths to apply transformations and enrich metadata.

3 Metadata extraction from TIF EOS file path

This section describes the operations applied to the TIF file path and Media Description tables to edit filenames and generate MARC fields. Renaming operations ensured unique filenames which were consistent with the envelope containment relationship. From these corrected filenames, we applied OpenRefine transformations to both tables to extract MARC fields.

3.1 Renaming adjustments

We first describe the transformations applied to remedy duplicate and erroneous filenames, as well as inconsistencies in envelope names, in order to ensure unique filenames that could be reliably linked to envelope media descriptions.

3.1.1 Resolving inconsistent filenames

Our criterion for renaming was as follows: if the first half of an underscore-separated filename did not contain the album folder name, we replaced this portion with the album folder name extracted from the file path. This ensured consistency between the true album directory hierarchy and the filenames contained within. Using this condition, we identified 194 files requiring modification (see Figure 9 for examples).

Album folder name	Original TIF filename	Updated TIF filename
24507X	_.tif	24507X_.tif
24588X	24589X_002.tif	24588X_002.tif
24588X	24589X_003.tif	24588X_003.tif
24588X	24589X_004.tif	24588X_004.tif
24588X	24589X_005.tif	24588X_005.tif
24588X	24589X_006.tif	24588X_006.tif
24588X	24589X_007.tif	24588X_007.tif
C0NV SIGN 11 X	C0NV SIGN 11 X_001.tif	C0NV SIGN 11 X_001.tif
41581X	41561X_006.tif	41581X_006.tif
41709X	41709 X_001.tif	41709X_001.tif
41709X	41709 X_002.tif	41709X_002.tif
41888X	41888 X_005.tif	41888X_005.tif
10018X	10018 X_003.tif	10018X_003.tif
10018X	10018 X_004.tif	10018X_004.tif
10019X	10019 X_004.tif	10019X_004.tif
10117X	10117 X_002.tif	10117X_002.tif
10158X	10058X002.tif	10158X_10058X002.tif

Figure 9: Table showing path-extracted album folder names, original erroneous filenames, and corrected filenames. The bottom row illustrates a special case where the renaming operation had an unintended effect: the true envelope name was prepended to the filename due to a missing underscore. While this breaks the intended filename structure, it reduces the risk of duplicates.

Corrected filenames were added in the "Updated TIF filename" column of our table. To prevent overwriting files, it was essential to verify the uniqueness of both original and updated filenames. We used OpenRefine's faceting functionality to obtain value counts of the updated and unaffected filenames, confirming that each filename occurred strictly once.

File renaming was executed directly on EOS using a Bash script, `rename_duplicate_files.sh`, which listed the necessary `mv` renaming commands. After each renaming operation, we ran the `list_tifs_recursive.sh` script (see Digitization GitLab project [2]) to regenerate the full list of file paths and check filenames and file counts.

In total, three renaming scripts were applied to correct erroneous filenames, including fixes for problematic spaces in file paths (see Section 8.1 for additional details). For envelopes that had been scanned twice, renaming decisions were made manually by inspecting album folder contents (see Section 8.3 for additional details).

3.1.2 Resolving mapping between filename to envelope ID

We aimed to ensure that album folder names extracted from the TIF file paths matched exactly with the envelope names in the Media Description table, so that the corresponding media information could be included in the MARC fields of the image records.

To check for the existence of such mappings, we used a General Refine Expression Language (GREL) `cross` operation on the envelope name column in both tables (see Code Snippet 2). When no match was found, the cross operation returned a blank value, which allowed us to visualize missing envelope-to-file relationships between Media Description and the List of TIF table, and vice versa.

```
cell.cross(List of TIF V3, 'TIF album ID').cells['TIF filename'].value.join(",")
```

Listing 2: GREL expression used to retrieve the list of files per folder name. The transformation was applied on the envelope name column of Media Description and matched to the 'TIF Album ID' column of the List of TIF file paths table. A missing match returned a blank value, while a match produced a comma-separated list of TIF files.

Through this process, we identified 30 envelope names in Media Description that could not be mapped to the List of TIF table, and 82 files in the List of TIF table with no corresponding envelope name in Media Description. We prioritized resolving the 82 missing file-to-envelope relationships, as they pointed to image files that existed in the file system, whereas unmatched albums in Media Description were of lesser concern since they did not correspond to actual files. The issue was resolved by correcting inconsistencies in envelope names within Media Description, typically by adjusting a single character or replacing a separator (see Section 8.2 for additional details). This procedure resulted in matching all 5344 albums in the TIF file path list to a media description.

3.2 MARC field extraction

To construct MARC snippets from the TIF file path and Media Description tables, we created each MARC field as a separate column in the TIF file path table. Since the CDS Invenio upload command `bibupload` (see CDS documentation [7]) required MARC snippets to be formatted in XML, we applied the XML formatting directly within the TIF file path table by wrapping the MARC column entries in XML syntax (see XML-ized MARC features in Figure 10b). This approach simplified the subsequent XML combination and export steps.

The table in Figure 10a summarizes the MARC fields created, along with the transformations applied to generate them.

MARC field	Meaning	Transformation
XML-001	Record ID	Incrementation by row in the table starting from first free available record ID: 2 485 832.
XML-037__a	Report number, i.e. image name	Stripped ".tif" from the filenames.
XML-110__a	Author	Invariant field: "CERN Photolab".
XML-245__a	Caption of image record	Format: "Image stored in envelope {envelopeNb}, Print N°{tirageNb}, Unknown caption" tirageNb extracted from the filename. If it is non-numeric, then the "Print N°{tirageNb}" is removed from the format. envelopeNb is the album folder name.
XML-260__c	Year of creation	Extracted from the envelope name and added "19" for all year numbers in a range of 50 to 90. Empty for envelope names with no date format.
XML-269__c	Date of creation	Extracted from the envelope name and conversion of the months to words. Empty for envelope names with no date format.
XML-500__a	General notes. We used this section to describe the envelope structure and storage context of our images.	Format: "Image found in storage room 500-S-023 – Envelope {envelope_Nb} – Contents of envelope:{media_description} – List of photos in envelope: {list_of_photos}" envelope_Nb was given by the album folder name extracted from the TIF path. media_description was joined from the Media Description table. Replace misspelled in media_description "Negetives" into "Negatives". List_of_photos was given by code snippet 2, then joined from the Media Description table.
XML-595__as	Specific notes for CDS. Subfield a indicates the main collection name. Subfield s indicates the scanning author.	Invariant fields: "Archive Collection" for subfield a, and "Scanned by Scancorner in 2024" for subfield s.
XML-690__a	Project name	Invariant field: "DIGITAL-MEMORY".
XML-8564__uqyz	Electronic location and access of TIF files. This section enables a TIF image file to be loaded to CDS and downloaded on CDS.	Subfield u: added filename to CDS upload url, "http://cern.ch/digital-memory/media-archiveimages/tracks/tiff/" Subfield y: added "TIFF Master File" to the filename. Subfield z: added filename and corresponding checksums.
XML-960__a	Display code, gives information on how the record should be formatted on CDS.	Invariant: "86".
XML-980__a	Collection ID	Invariant: "TRACKSIMAGES".
XML-999__a	Content type	Invariant: "IMAGE".

(a) Table showing a list of MARC fields that were added as columns to the TIF file path table, their meaning, and an intuitive description of the MARC extraction transformations. Constant MARC fields are indicated as such with "Invariant". Transformations were implemented in GREL and Python, and can be found on the OpenRefine table history (see Digitization GitLab [2]). A complete description of checksum extraction is provided in section 4.

XML-001 <controlfield tag="001">2516929</controlfield>	XML-037__a <datafield tag="037" ind1=" " ind2=" " "><subfield code="a">01-4-56X_001</subfield></datafield>	XML-110__a <datafield tag="110" ind1=" " ind2=" " "><subfield code="a">CERN Photolab</subfield></datafield>	XML-245__a <datafield tag="245" ind1=" " ind2=" " "><subfield code="a">Image stored in envelope 01-4-56X, Print N°1, Unknown caption</subfield></datafield>	XML-269__c <datafield tag="269" ind1=" " ind2=" " "><subfield code="c">1 Apr 1956</subfield></datafield>	XML-260__c <datafield tag="260" ind1=" " ind2=" " "><subfield code="c">1956</subfield></datafield>	XML-500__a <datafield tag="500" ind1=" " ind2=" " "><subfield code="a">Image found in storage room 500-S-023 - Envelope 01-4-56X - Contents of envelope: 2x Medium Format, 1x Photos - List of photos in envelope: 01-4-56X_001, 01-4-56X_002, 01-4-56X_003</subfield></datafield>
XML-595__as <datafield tag="595" ind1=" " ind2=" " "><subfield code="a">Archive Collection</subfield><subfield code="s">Scanned by ScanCorner in 2024</subfield></datafield>	XML-690__a <datafield tag="690" ind1=" " ind2=" " "><subfield code="a">DIGITAL-MEMORY</subfield></datafield>	XML-8564__uqyz <datafield tag="856" ind1="4" ind2=" " "><subfield code="u">http://cern.ch/digital-memory/media-archive/image/tracks/tiff/01-4-56X_001.tif</subfield><subfield code="y">TIFF Master File 01-4-56X_001.tif</subfield><subfield code="z">(ORIGINAL:MD5)01-4-56X_001.tif:9c44b497b61d292a7e54af56b17719af</subfield></datafield>	XML-960__a <datafield tag="960" ind1=" " ind2=" " "><subfield code="a">86</subfield></datafield>	XML-980__a <datafield tag="980" ind1=" " ind2=" " "><subfield code="a">TRACKSIMAGES</subfield></datafield>	XML-999__a <datafield tag="999" ind1=" " ind2=" " "><subfield code="a">IMAGE</subfield></datafield>	

(b) MARC fields formatted as XML, for image record 01-4-56X_001.

Figure 10: Description of transformations applied to the TIF file path table and Media Description tables in 10a. Illustration of resulting XML MARC fields for one image record in 10b. MARC fields are shown on both tables as XML-{datafield}_[subfield_list], where datafield is the MARC datafield and subfield_list is the concatenated list of subfields.

4 Data transformations for MARC fields

This section describes the Python scripts executed on the initial list of TIF files to complete the creation of MARC snippets. These transformations required accessing the image source files in order to (1) collect additional metadata fields and (2) generate intermediate files and computations needed for CDS upload.

In particular, we computed image checksums, deduplicated similar images to identify distinct items in the collection, and created JPG versions of the filtered images for download and display on CDS (see Figure 11 for an overview of the pipeline).

Figure 11: Overview of the image transformation pipeline. The left panel shows the flow common to the image similarity script `compare_images.py`, the image clustering script `cluster_images.py`, and the JPG conversion script `convert_images.py`. Inputs were PHOTOS-separated TIF path .xlsx files exported from OpenRefine. Log files were generated during the execution of each script for every PHOTOS batch. The right panel shows the outputs of the transformation scripts. The script `generate_md5_checksums.sh` was the only standalone script, independent of the TIF path lists.

4.1 Checksum extraction

Checksums were added to the electronic access MARC field (XML-8564, subfield z) to uniquely identify the digital image content. We extracted image checksums using a Bash script that recursively searched for TIF files from the root folder of the collection and applied the `md5sum` command to each file. The results were stored in a .csv file indexed by the TIF file path.

By using the TIF file path as a joining column, we incorporated the checksums into the XML-8564_uqyz column of the main TIF file path table, thereby completing the electronic access field.

4.2 Image similarity

This section explains how we addressed the challenge of having near-identical images within the same album folder of our collection. Our goal was to design an approach that could both (1) assess the extent of the similarity problem and (2) provide intermediate metrics to guide decision-making and apply thresholds for selecting representative images from clusters of similar ones.

To avoid overloading CDS, we chose to upload only a relevant subset of distinct images. This selected fraction was then used to generate reference URLs pointing to other images in the same envelope.

4.2.1 Intuition

Our intuition was to compute similarity scores algorithmically between pairs of images. Since we assumed that similar content appeared only within the same album folder due to the scanning procedure, we restricted comparisons to the folder level, which contained an average of five images (see Figure 14a).

We interpreted the comparison scores as edge weights in a graph linking together all images within a folder. After thresholding these edge weights, similar images appeared in the same connected component of the similarity graph, while distinct images belonged to separate components. From this album folder graph structure, representative images could be selected for each component, thereby preserving a meaningful fraction of the collection (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: Illustration of the image similarity logic for album folder 10074. Analog negatives in an envelope were digitized into near-identical images within the corresponding album folder. Pairwise comparisons within the folder can be interpreted as a similarity graph. Representative images were then selected for each connected component of the graph.

4.2.2 Similarity Algorithm

Since our approach required comparing over 32000 images across 5400 albums, we prioritized a lightweight similarity solution available in Python.

We selected ORB (Oriented FAST and Rotated BRIEF) [6], a feature detection and description algorithm implemented in the Open Source Computer Vision library (OpenCV) library. ORB is a fusion of two methods, the FAST keypoint detector and the BRIEF descriptor, making it both efficient and accurate for image matching.

In ORB, keypoints are informative pixel locations detected in an image, while descriptors are binary vectors describing the neighborhood of each keypoint.

We used ORB to match the descriptors of two images, for example, descriptors `des1` and `des2` from images `image_1` and `image_2`. We used a Brute Force Matcher (`BFMatcher`) to match the two image descriptors with the Hamming distance, which is a well-suited distance

for binary vectors. The matcher produced a list of matches, linking a descriptor `des1_i` in `image_1` to its closest descriptor `des2_j` in `image_2`. The average distance across all matches was normalized and converted to a similarity percentage (see Code Snippet 3).

```
# 1. Get image descriptors
kp1, des1 = orb.detectAndCompute(image_1, None)
kp2, des2 = orb.detectAndCompute(image_2, None)

# 2. Match descriptors
bf = cv2.BFMatcher(cv2.NORM_HAMMING, crossCheck=True)
matches = bf.match(des1, des2)

# 3. Get similarity percentage
distances = [m.distance for m in matches]
max_distance = 256 # Max Hamming distance for ORB
similarity = 100 * (1 - np.mean(distances) / max_distance)
```

Listing 3: Similarity percentage computation between two images, using ORB by OpenCV.

As image similarity is a long-studied problem in computer vision, we also qualitatively tested other approaches on toy examples with artificially introduced anomalies. In particular, we compared ORB with (1) histogram-based similarity (`cv2.calcHist` in OpenCV) and (2) the Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) from the `scikit-image` library. For each method, we verified whether thresholding could effectively separate anomalous images from a folder containing similar images. The choice of ORB was motivated by its accuracy and faster runtime in such examples, compared to the other two solutions.

Ultimately, we adopted ORB as a proof of concept to demonstrate how similarity scores could be used to cluster near-identical images and retain only representative ones. Our focus was on building a working similarity-driven clustering framework rather than performing an exhaustive benchmarking of algorithms. For future work on benchmarking and image similarity analysis, the pipeline’s similarity score function, defined between two images to output a similarity percentage, can be replaced and tested with alternatives.

The following sections describe the implementation of the comparison and clustering routines, which were based on the ORB similarity function.

4.2.3 Generating similarity scores

We created similarity scores for all pairs of images within each album folder. We ran the script `compare_images.py` on the original TIF path list table to obtain an output comparison table, with the filenames for each pairwise image comparison, the album folder name that they belonged to, and, finally, the similarity percentage scores (see Figure 13).

4.2.4 Clustering images

We used the script `cluster_images.py` to identify image groups and select representative images, working from the similarity scores generated in Section 4.2.3.

Connected components were identified by constructing envelope-wise graph representations. Edges were added between two images whose similarity score exceeded a similarity threshold, meaning they could be considered near-identical. We then used a depth-first search traversal of the graph to visit the neighbors of the image nodes and find connected components of the graph. A decision rule was put in place to select the lowest file size image as the representative image of a component. This was motivated by (1) the fact that larger file sizes could induce

1. Generating similarity percentage scores

70,057 rows			
Show as: rows records Show: 5 10 25 50 100 500 1000 rows			
All	TIF album ID	Comparison	Similarity Score (%)
1.	10850X	10850X_001.tif VS. 10850X_002.tif	87.68203883495146
2.	10850X	10850X_001.tif VS. 10850X_003.tif	87.89574795081967
3.	10850X	10850X_002.tif VS. 10850X_003.tif	89.29217706013362
4.	11051X	11051X_001.tif VS. 11051X_002.tif	87.42287022292994
5.	11051X	11051X_001.tif VS. 11051X_003.tif	87.13394261006289
6.	11051X	11051X_002.tif VS. 11051X_003.tif	93.89500473484848
7.	11052X	11052X_001.tif VS. 11052X_002.tif	86.42347440944881
8.	11052X	11052X_001.tif VS. 11052X_003.tif	85.23976293103448
9.	11052X	11052X_002.tif VS. 11052X_003.tif	93.51017068788501

2. Clustering the similarity scores

6,366 rows					
Show as: rows records Show: 5 10 25 50 100 500 1000 rows << first					
All	album_id	filename	File Size (MB)	Component ID	Images per cluster
1.	10850X	10850X_003.tif	27	Component_0	3
2.	11051X	11051X_002.tif	28	Component_0	3
3.	11052X	11052X_001.tif	50	Component_0	3
4.	11053X	11053X_001.tif	46	Component_0	3
5.	11054X	11054X_001.tif	56	Component_0	3
6.	11055X	11055X_001.tif	66	Component_0	3
7.	11056X	11056X_001.tif	53	Component_0	3
8.	11057X	11057X_001.tif	59	Component_0	3
9.	11058X	11058X_003.tif	47	Component_0	3
10.	11059X	11059X_002.tif	35	Component_0	2
11.	11059X	11059X_001.tif	58	Component_1	1

3 images in one envelope:
3 similarity scores

Component 1 image

Component 0 image

Figure 13: OpenRefine tables for similarity scores and clustering.

Left panel: comparison table for all images in the collection. Since comparisons were made at the folder level and there was an average of five images for around 5400 folders, this created comparisons in the magnitude of $(5 + 4 + 3 + 3 + 1) \cdot 5400 \approx 80000$, which roughly corresponds to the 70000 rows in the table.

Right panel: clustering table with image filenames selected from components that were grouped from the similarity scores of the comparison table. The "Component ID" column shows the one (or more) connected component ID found within an album folder. "Images per cluster" gives the original count of images in the component, which were collapsed into one representative image indicated in "filename".

Bottom panel: graph visualizations of the tables for an example folder containing three envelopes. The comparison table draws edges with similarity weights between images in the same album folder. The clustering table removes edges below a similarity threshold (82%) and identifies connected components, selecting one image per component.

space limitations and hinder subsequent JPG creation and upload, and (2) the fact that larger images could capture irrelevant smudges.

A clustering table was used to store information about the connected components and representative images chosen for each component (see Figure 13).

4.2.5 Threshold determination for clustering

(a) Histogram of original file counts. File counts are equally distributed from one to nine images per album, with a peak at seven images.

(b) Histogram of post-clustering file counts, with similarity threshold 82%. File counts are concentrated at one file per album.

(c) Barplot of file count reduction per album, with a 70% similarity threshold.

(d) Barplot of file count reduction per album, with a 82% similarity threshold.

Figure 14: Visualization of clustering-induced file count reduction. Histograms in 14a and 14b show the number of images per album on the x-axis and the album count on the y-axis. Barplots in 14c and 14d compare the original file count (pink) and reduced post-clustering file count (purple) (y-axis) per album (x-axis).

The effect of the threshold value for clustering was visualized through barplots created by `evaluate_clustering.py`, comparing original file counts to post-clustering file counts per album folder. By analyzing these plots, we could intuitively find a satisfactory threshold range for the clustering procedure (see Figure 14d and 14c).

A threshold value of 70% (see Figure 14c) produced a flat reduction profile, erasing meaningful distinctions between images and collapsing almost all album folders into a single image. A lower threshold implies a more lenient identity criterion, which tends to merge all images into the same connected component. In contrast, a range of 82 to 85% yielded a spiked reduction profile (see Figure 14d), indicating that meaningful visual differences were preserved, while near-duplicates managed to be grouped together. We manually inspected five to ten album folders, including both near-duplicates and visually distinct images, to validate the choice of the threshold.

Given a reasonable threshold value of 82%, validated by several album folder examples, we observed that the clustering procedure effectively reduced a significant fraction of album folders to a single representative file (see Figure 14b). This significant shift in the file count distribution justified our image deduplication approach, as it suggested that a large part of our collection contained duplicates.

Finally, by taking the 6366 filenames from the 82% thresholded clustering table and ensuring the presence of the initial 5344 album folders, we refined our original TIF file path table to

include only the representative images identified in the clustering step. Album folders containing only label files were discarded, leaving 5339 album folders. The record IDs for this selection were then recomputed by incrementing from the first available record ID.

The resulting list of TIF paths will be referred to as the 82%-threshold TIF file path table.

4.2.6 URL references for images in the same envelope

In addition to the existing MARC fields, we sought to enhance user navigation of the collection by including links to other images from the same envelope. This approach allowed the collection to be intuitively explored following the original envelope structure.

We based this operation on the 82%-threshold TIF file path table, as it contained the images that would be accessible on CDS as records.

To implement this, we created the references MARC field (XML-773), with URLs pointing to image records from the same envelope, i.e. images originating from the same album folder in the digitized collection.

Each URL was formatted as a CDS search query, targeting the report number of the image (XML-037_a) and the collection name, "Tracks Images." For a given image record, the references section aggregated XML-773 fields, each containing a single search URL to another image in the same envelope (see XML snippet 4).

```
<datafield tag="773" ind1=" " ind2=" "><subfield code="p">Related image
↪ 01-4-56X_001</subfield><subfield code="u">https://cds.cern.ch/
↪ search?cc=Tracks+Images&amp;p=037__a%3A%2201-4-56X_001%22&amp;of=hd</
↪ subfield></datafield>
<datafield tag="773" ind1=" " ind2=" "><subfield code="p">Related image
↪ 01-4-56X_002</subfield><subfield code="u">https://cds.cern.ch/
↪ search?cc=Tracks+Images&amp;p=037__a%3A%2201-4-56X_002%22&amp;of=hd</
↪ subfield></datafield>
```

Listing 4: Example of a MARC XML-773_up section for image 01-4-56X_003. The two data fields in this section correspond to the two other images from the same envelope: 01-4-56X_001 and 01-4-56X_002. The subfield p is the text of the link, and the subfield u is the CDS search URL, querying the image names. "&" was used in place of "&" and "%22" in place of spaces for XML URL formatting.

4.3 JPEG creation

We converted our filtered TIF image collection into JPG files to enable the download option on CDS. This entailed creating 3 sizes of JPG images specified by widths of 180, 640 and 1440 pixels, to enable various download sizes on CDS. We first created a script `convert_images.py` to convert the TIF images into JPG images of the 3 required widths. Then, we incorporated the JPG file paths into an FFT ("fulltext file transfer") section in the image record MARC snippets to enable their upload to CDS.

4.3.1 JPG creation

The script `convert_images.py` iterated over the 82%-threshold TIF file path table to load TIF images, resize them to widths 180, 640, and 1440, and finally save the resized images as JPG files in a temporary storage directory. We used a public CERN Andrew File System (AFS) workspace for that purpose.

The conversion to JPG handled heterogeneous image modes: the RGB mode (8-bit color mode) and the L mode (8-bit grayscale mode) could directly be resized and saved as JPG, while

the I mode (16-bit grayscale mode) first needed to undergo pixel value normalization and L conversion before JPG conversion.

The files were named according to the following format: `reportNb_iconwidth.jpg`, where `reportNb` is the report number (XML-037_a) and `width` is the pixel width of the image, one of 180, 640, or 1440.

During the conversion process, we discovered that `10848X_003.tif` (record ID 2491721) was a corrupted image because it could not be converted. It was therefore removed from the final list of uploaded files, but the initial record ID ordering of the TIF path list was preserved.

4.3.2 MARC Fulltext File Transfer formatting

JPG paths were then included into an FFT section in the MARC snippet for upload to CDS (see XML snippet 5).

```
<datafield tag="FFT" ind1=" " ind2=" "><subfield code="a">
↪ /afs/cern.ch/work/d/dbrousta/public/tracks_images_jpg/10850X_003_icon1440.jpg</subfield>
↪ <subfield code="t">Image</subfield><subfield code="d">Image
↪ 10850X_003</subfield><subfield code="f">jpg;icon-1440</subfield></datafield>
<datafield tag="FFT" ind1=" " ind2=" "><subfield code="a">
↪ /afs/cern.ch/work/d/dbrousta/public/tracks_images_jpg/10850X_003_icon640.jpg</subfield>
↪ <subfield code="t">Image</subfield><subfield code="d">Image
↪ 10850X_003</subfield><subfield code="f">jpg;icon-640</subfield></datafield>
<datafield tag="FFT" ind1=" " ind2=" "><subfield code="a">
↪ /afs/cern.ch/work/d/dbrousta/public/tracks_images_jpg/10850X_003_icon180.jpg</subfield>
↪ <subfield code="t">Image</subfield><subfield code="d">Image
↪ 10850X_003</subfield><subfield code="f">jpg;icon-180</subfield></datafield>
```

Listing 5: MARC FFT section for image `10850X_003` for JPG upload to CDS. There are 3 data fields for each image size. Within a data field, subfield `a` contains the path of the image, subfield `d` contains the original image name, and subfield `f` is the width of the image in pixels.

5 Upload to the CERN Document Server

After processing the images in our collection and extracting the required MARC fields, we took care of the upload of the 6365 images in the collection, spanning 5339 envelopes.

5.1 Finalizing the MARC XML snippets for the collection

The final MARC XML was produced by concatenating all field components into a single string, by adding each feature sequentially and separating them by newlines for readability. Because XML does not rely on indentation, formatting was straightforward. Blank values, which were occasionally found in date or URL reference fields, were represented as empty strings. For each image record, a MARC XML snippet was generated by applying a GREL expression to the 82%-threshold TIF path list (see Code Snippet 6). Each snippet was enclosed within `<record>` and `</record>` tags to delimit the image record.

```
'<record>' + forEach([
  cells['XML-001'].value,
  cells['XML-037__a'].value,
  cells['XML-110__a'].value,
  cells['XML-245__a'].value,
  cells['XML-260__c'].value,
  cells['XML-269__c'].value,
  cells['XML-500__a'].value,
  cells['XML-595__as'].value,
  cells['XML-596__a'].value,
  cells['XML-690__a'].value,
  cells['XML-773__up'].value,
  cells['XML-8564__uqyz'].value,
  cells['XML-FFT'].value,
  cells['XML-960__a'].value,
  cells['XML-980__a'].value,
  cells['XML-999__a'].value], xml,
  if(isNull(xml), '',
  ↪ xml.strip()+'\n')).join('') + '</record>'
```

Listing 6: GREL expression to create the final MARC XML snippet.

MARC XML snippets were divided into six batches of 1000 records. For each batch, we generated a corresponding .xml file, enclosed within `<xml>` and `</xml>` tags, containing the MARC XML snippets. These files then served as input for the upload commands.

5.2 Moving the TIF files

Before executing the upload commands, the TIF files of the collection had to first be moved to the CDS image path. To avoid overwriting any existing CDS source files, we added the `tracks/tiff` folder on the CDS images path, where our collection would be transferred.

We created `cp` commands for each image record in TIF file path table in the "Move command to cds" column to move the source TIF files to the CDS images directory under the `tracks/tiff/` directory. These commands were formatted as `[! -e "destination_path"] && cp "source_path" "destination_path" || echo "source_path" >> skipped_file s.txt`, with `destination_path` as the CDS destination path, and `source_path` as the source TIF file path.

We used the `cp` command instead of `mv` to safely transfer files to the CDS destination path while retaining an original copy of the structured dataset. Quotation marks around the paths were used to account for spaces in the filenames. The command first checked whether the TIF source file already existed in the destination path. If it did not, then the `cp` command was executed. Otherwise, the `cp` command was skipped, and the TIF source path was added to `skipped_files.txt` for later inspection.

5.3 CDS Upload

Figure 15: Portfolio view of the first 100 image records of the Tracks Images collection [12]

The six batches of `.xml` files containing the MARC XML snippets for all image records in our collection were uploaded to CDS using the `bibupload` command.

Before the full batch upload, we tested several example image records, specifically to check the effect of spaces within file paths. We concluded that spaces were tolerated in the report number (in XML-037), in the source TIF file path (in XML-8564) and in the JPG file paths (in XML-FFT). However, spaces had to be replaced by `"%22"` in the search URLs of the references section (XML-773), as required by the XML format.

The upload process began by establishing a connection to a CDS node. We then used `xmllint` and `xmlmarclint` to check the formatting of the `.xml` files. Finally, we executed `bibupload` commands for each of the six batches of `.xml`, using the `--force` parameter to create the records on the fly, ensuring that no other record insertion process could interfere with their allocation.

The Tracks Images collection of 6365 images was uploaded on 08/08/25 on the CERN Photolab page (see Figure 15 and Figure 16 for image record display on CDS).

(a) Three image records from Tracks Images on CDS from envelope 01-4-56X.

(b) Caption, author, download links, notes, and related images for image record 1-4-56X_003.

Figure 16: Layout of image records in the Tracks Images collection [12] on CDS.

6 Conclusion

In this project, we analyzed a recently digitized collection of photos documenting CERN’s early history, and uploaded it to CDS to ensure its long-term preservation and visibility. The collection contained particle tracks originating from a detector technology known as the Hydrogen Bubble Chamber, which inspired the collection’s name, Tracks Images.

Our workflow began by examining the envelope structure of the analog collection to identify extractable metadata. We then populated relevant MACXML metadata fields to create a first layer of descriptive information. To reduce redundancy from multiple scans of the same negatives, we applied an image similarity algorithm to cluster near-identical images. Finally, from the clustered and filtered set, we generated MARCXML records and uploaded them to CDS. The result is a collection of 6365 image records, covering 5339 envelopes, now available on CDS (see Tracks Images collection [12]).

While this marks an important milestone, several challenges and opportunities for future work still remain for improving the collection.

6.1 Alternative similarity approaches

Although the ORB feature detection algorithm provided a practical baseline for computing similarity scores, our benchmarking was limited and does not guarantee that ORB is the most suitable choice.

To revisit this aspect, future work could establish a labeled ground-truth dataset of similarity groupings to allow systematic benchmarking of different algorithms and thresholds. Such an evaluation would help to understand the trade-offs in thresholding: higher thresholds preserve more unique images at the risk of duplicates, whereas lower thresholds remove duplicates but risk discarding valuable content.

The heterogeneity of the collection, spanning variations in color, resolution, and edge structure, adds another layer of complexity to the image similarity problem: a similarity threshold choice that works for one subset of images may fail to generalize for another.

The pipeline was designed with modularity in mind for the choice of similarity algorithm: once an improved method is identified, the similarity function `compute_similarity_orb` of the

compare_images.py can be replaced directly to run the comparison and clustering pipeline for image deduplication.

6.2 Correcting scanning mistakes

(a) Image 11076X_001.

Secondary particle	10 ⁰	10 ¹	10 ²	10 ³	10 ⁴	10 ⁵	10 ⁶	10 ⁷	10 ⁸	10 ⁹	10 ¹⁰	10 ¹¹	10 ¹²	10 ¹³	10 ¹⁴	10 ¹⁵	10 ¹⁶	10 ¹⁷	10 ¹⁸	10 ¹⁹	10 ²⁰	10 ²¹	10 ²²	10 ²³	10 ²⁴	10 ²⁵	10 ²⁶	10 ²⁷	10 ²⁸	10 ²⁹	10 ³⁰	10 ³¹	10 ³²	10 ³³	10 ³⁴	10 ³⁵	10 ³⁶	10 ³⁷	10 ³⁸	10 ³⁹	10 ⁴⁰	10 ⁴¹	10 ⁴²	10 ⁴³	10 ⁴⁴	10 ⁴⁵	10 ⁴⁶	10 ⁴⁷	10 ⁴⁸	10 ⁴⁹	10 ⁵⁰	10 ⁵¹	10 ⁵²	10 ⁵³	10 ⁵⁴	10 ⁵⁵	10 ⁵⁶	10 ⁵⁷	10 ⁵⁸	10 ⁵⁹	10 ⁶⁰	10 ⁶¹	10 ⁶²	10 ⁶³	10 ⁶⁴	10 ⁶⁵	10 ⁶⁶	10 ⁶⁷	10 ⁶⁸	10 ⁶⁹	10 ⁷⁰	10 ⁷¹	10 ⁷²	10 ⁷³	10 ⁷⁴	10 ⁷⁵	10 ⁷⁶	10 ⁷⁷	10 ⁷⁸	10 ⁷⁹	10 ⁸⁰	10 ⁸¹	10 ⁸²	10 ⁸³	10 ⁸⁴	10 ⁸⁵	10 ⁸⁶	10 ⁸⁷	10 ⁸⁸	10 ⁸⁹	10 ⁹⁰	10 ⁹¹	10 ⁹²	10 ⁹³	10 ⁹⁴	10 ⁹⁵	10 ⁹⁶	10 ⁹⁷	10 ⁹⁸	10 ⁹⁹	10 ¹⁰⁰
--------------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	------------------	-------------------

(b) Image 11071X_002.

(c) Image 11055X_001.

Figure 17: Example of scanning mistakes for three images in the Tracks Images collection. 17a is rotated by 90°, and both 17c and 17b are flipped upside down.

To further enhance the accessibility and reliability of the collection, future work could also address scanning errors introduced during the digitization process. Such errors, which often appear in figures and diagrams (see Figure 17 for examples), can hinder both automated metadata extraction and human interpretation. Correcting them would improve the accuracy of the records and ensure a better user experience.

6.3 Keyword extraction for metadata enrichment

(a) French organizational diagram 12683X_002.

(b) Chinese-captionned celestial profile 01-2-56X_011.

(c) English scientific diagram 11055X_001.

Figure 18: Illustration of language diversity in the images of the collection.

As our collection is highly heterogeneous in data but sparse in metadata, metadata enrichment by keyword extraction could not only provide additional contextual information, but also help to identify themes and categories across the collection.

Automatic detection of graph axes could provide estimates of energy scales, while figure captions could replace “Unknown caption” placeholders. Multilingual content across the collection (see Figure 18 for examples) could potentially be used to define subcategories in the collection.

6.4 Metadata curation

Finally, expert-based metadata curation could provide an additional layer of enrichment to the collection. The collection is now publicly accessible with minimal information, but expert input could help to infer context for precise cataloging and captioning. Tools such as the “Suggest a caption” feature on CDS can serve as entry points for such contributions. Engaging the help of former CERN personnel who worked with CERN’s past technologies could also be meaningful in recovering missing knowledge and context. Such efforts would also enable cross-linking the collection with other digitized CDS collections, such as the Particle Collisions collection [11], which overlaps thematically with the Tracks Images collection.

7 References

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8 Appendix

8.1 Renaming inconsistent filenames

During the first renaming round (`rename_duplicate_files.sh`), we encountered issues caused by spaces in file paths, as these were not enclosed in quotation marks. In the second renaming round (`rename_duplicate_files_run2.sh`), this was resolved by replacing spaces in both filenames and album folder names with dashes.

However, this fix also introduced a new issue: the path separator "/" between album folders and filenames was mistakenly replaced with a dash. As a result, several files lost their mapping to an album folder and instead duplicated the envelope ID within the filename. Since filenames were already unique at this stage, we chose not to re-run the renaming script but instead corrected the mappings manually in the TIF path table.

The following files required manual mapping back to their correct album folders:

- C0NV-SIGN-11-X_C0NV-SIGN-11-X_001.tif → C0NV SIGN 11 X
- C0NV-SIGN-11-X_C0NV-SIGN-11-X_Label.tif → C0NV SIGN 11 X
- CONV-SIGN-10-X_CONV-SIGN-10-X_Label.tif → CONV SIGN 10 X
- CONV-SIGN-9-X_CONV-SIGN-9-X_001.tif → CONV SIGN 9 X
- CONV-SIGN-9-X_CONV-SIGN-9-X_Label.tif → CONV SIGN 9 X

In addition to these, a few files were missed during the renaming process: 25283X_008.tif, 41364 X_001.tif, 41372 X_002.tif, 41377 X_002.tif, 41381 X_001.tif. Since the collection already had unique filenames, no further renaming was performed.

8.2 Resolving mapping from filename to envelope ID

We also made adjustments to ensure consistency between envelope IDs in the Media Description table and album folder names in the TIF path list table. Most of these corrections involved single-digit errors, missing zeros, or separator inconsistencies.

Corrections included:

- 1-3-58X → 01-3-58X
- 1-4-65X → 01-4-65X
- 01-5-65X → 01-5-68X
- 02-5.68X → 02-5-68X
- 8-12-55X → 08-12-55X

Each correction was validated against the Media Description string to confirm that the number of digitized files in a folder matched the expected count.

8.3 Duplicate scans

Finally, we identified a small number of envelopes that had been scanned twice, resulting in duplicate digitized folders. This occurred for:

- Envelopes 25292X and 25929X,
- Envelopes 1-4-65X and 01-4-65X.

Manual inspection of the envelope label photos confirmed that 25929X was correct, and 25292X was erroneous. Accordingly, the 25292X folder was deleted.

For the second case, the Media Description table entry for 1-4-65X was corrected to 01-4-65X. No files were deleted, but rows referring to the incorrect path were removed from the TIF path table.

